
Unlocking the Potential of Fintech in India: Addressing Implementation Issues

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Abstract

Fintech has revolutionized and transformed the whole Indian financial industry, providing us with innovative solutions and fueling the growth of this transformation. This paper examines and addresses the key issues and problems that hinder implementing fintech in the Indian context. This study is beneficial from a stakeholder perspective, including policymakers, shareholders, employees, investors, and industry practitioners, to address the immense potential that mitigates the implementation issue and contributes to the economy growth in India. This study is based on secondary sources such as research papers, reports, and current articles to address the problem of fintech implementation in India.

Keywords: *Fintech, Implementation, Issues, Indian context, stakeholder perspective*

JEL Classification Number: O3, O4

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1. Introduction

“Fintech implementation is adopting technology to provide financial solutions to existing businesses and transforming the overall financial industry using technology to create innovative solutions that improve efficiency, accessibility, and user experience in the fintech industry.”

In recent years, the growth of fintech tremendously, huge investment in Indian economy. The advancement of fintech, such as artificial technology, Unified payment interference, mobile banking, digital identity plays a significant role to enable innovative products and services and provide effective solutions in fintech industry ^[1].

Fintech represent the several opportunities and challenges for the traditional financial institutions but offer the innovative and customer centric solutions that disrupt the whole Indian financial ecosystem ^[2]. Fintech is the integration of crowdfunding, credit sourcing, lending, and the stock market into existing banking and financial services ^[3].

Fintech implementations promote inclusivity, improve customer experience and adopt cost effective solutions for financial services. The fintech implementation has diverse potential to recreate the financial ecosystem that provides cost effective and efficient solutions to the customer and implement innovative fintech solutions for the financial services ^[4] ^[5].

Indian Fintech adoption is higher than the global average by 23%, showing the willingness of consumers and businesses to adopt digital financial solutions. Projections suggest that the Indian fintech market could reach \$1 trillion by 2030 with revenues of up to \$200 billion, indicating the substantial growth potential and opportunities in the financial sector. Fintech growth has tremendous potential to significantly impact the Indian economy. The \$7.8 billion invested in the fintech market in 2021 underscores strong investor interest and support for local startups working on empowering them to innovate and expand to enhance the fintech ecosystem ^[6].

Fintech enabled the technological advancements into business models to generate revenue and enrich entrepreneurship. Fintech solutions utilize new business frameworks to improve financial accessibility for businesses and consumers. Fintech reshapes engagement with financial products and services to disrupt traditional financial services, enhancing efficiency, reducing costs and improving customer experiences.

The shift from cash to digital payment is a significant challenge for promoting digital literacy and addressing the challenges of advancing towards a cashless economy. In a competitive market with over 4200 active fintech startups in India, their role in innovative financial products and services is to satisfy customer needs ^[7].

The Fintech Industry is transformed towards growth, high adoption rates, and increasing investment, which promises the future of the Indian economy. Despite several challenges related to payment methods, awareness and accessibility will be steps to sustaining this momentum.

The innovation process of implementation significantly transforms financial services, enhances efficiency and effectiveness, and adds value to lighten the production, marking,

logistics, and transportation system [8] Fintech implementation enhances the efficiency of automating processes, reduces paperwork that promotes innovation and competitiveness, encourages novel products and services for their development that are beneficial to the consumer, and advances financial inclusion to provide access to underserved populations and brighten the security and regulatory measures that protect financial services and accomplish growth in the economy in India [9]. Despite advancement and growth, key issues hinder the implementation of fintech in India, and the paper aims to address fintech implementation issues to contribute the economic development in India.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The innovative fintech significantly impacts banking services, where identified drivers and challenges are a competitive advantage for the banking. The issues related to the implementation of the innovative fintech were undermined and persist for solving. Implementing innovative strategies creates a competitive advantage for banking and financial services. For that, the effective implementation of fintech is transforming the banking services that lead to the growth of the Indian economy [10].

The studies focus on exploring themes related to networking technology, innovative fintech, disruptive fintech, growth of business models, and soundness and risk that are implicated in banking and financial services for the future [11].

The study analysis requires the practitioner to have a collective understanding of the term fintech. The author emphasizes that a well-defined definition of *fintech* is the foundation for the research community to conduct research. Researchers claim in this paper that there is no one definition of fintech. Researchers identified a gap in this paper, as neither academia nor practitioners identify fintech as its origin. The reason behind this is the lack of evidence that claims to be the sole source of fintech. [12]. The impact of Fintech on three viewpoints, including consumers, market participants, and the regulatory front, can be utilized to understand how Fintech affects various stakeholders. The study finds a gap in this paper because studies need to include all the necessary products, processes, disruption, and transformation development and implementation required for Fintech, which is still in its infancy [13].

The study examines Bitcoin and blockchain through a literature review and discovers the novelty of fintech innovation in neobanks. A gap in the study is that the researcher focuses on exploring blockchain technology, bitcoin, neo banks, and all other areas of fintech that need to be explored [14]. Financial institutions, regulators, and politicians can gain valuable insights from a study on Fintech and its implications when deciding whether to use the technology based on regulatory considerations. Stakeholders can better understand what is helpful to create for developing cooperative partnerships for Fintech development and showing potential hazards in adopting Fintech by identifying prolific journals, authors, institutions, countries, and areas in Fintech. For sustainability, information from talent management in financial institutions gives valuable insights. Identify a gap study limited to a Fintech overview through bibliometric analysis that does not include implementation challenges, regulatory concerns, and trends in Fintech that are used in keywords and citations

A study investigating digitalization's effects on the banking sector focuses on the alliances between banks and fintech. The study aims to determine the bank's potential for alliances and how they add to the growing body of knowledge on individual-based business models in the fintech industry. These alliances have the potential to reshape traditional banking models, enhance the customer experience, and introduce innovative financial services. The study's findings show that neither the other bank nor fintech characteristics significantly affect the value of the bank in the context of a fintech alliance. Identifying a gap study that does not cover: What is the reason for digital services to focus on the development of fintech rather than comparing it with the competition of large incubators? ^[16]

The studies show the potential impact of specialized fintech firms hindering the traditional financial intermediation related to peer-to-peer lending and the interaction between fintech and banking in the context of lower trust in banks, leading to higher participation in alternative lending models like peer-to-peer loans. The interaction between fintech and banking is a dynamic process involving competition, collaboration, and regulatory implications. Identify a gap that the study has not covered or challenges, and do not emphasize the implementation of fintech ^[17]. In studies to combat global poverty, it is essential to prioritize constructing a corpus of information systems research on fintech-led financial inclusivity. The study's gap is limited to establishing a structure for planning IS research on financial inclusion in fintech rather than highlighting the practical implementation and evaluation stages ^[18]. Mobile payment services play a crucial role in vertical fintech. These services are expected to have a significant impact on the fintech industry. A persistent challenge is crucial to observe for educating the public, who are potential customers, about the optimal utilization of banking-oriented financial services. A gap in that study is limited to the implementation of technology, efficiency, and a framework for assessing the level of confidence in fintech among micro, small, and medium enterprises ^[19].

Findings demonstrate user satisfaction, gamification, and payment applications, as well as their impact on user behavior—the positive impact of gamification and payment applications on user satisfaction and intention to continue usage. Hedonic gratification factors are enjoyments derived from gamification elements that significantly influence user satisfaction and their intention to keep using the m-payment application. A gap in that study is that focusing solely on the Indonesian sample population restricts the generalizability of the findings to other countries with different social-demographic characteristics ^[20]. The Fintech ontology theory is still in its initial stages and has not been disclosed and explored extensively, suggesting more exploration and investigation is needed. The gap as identified, ontology theory is still in its initial stages and has not been disclosed and explored extensively, which suggests a need for more exploration and investigation. In a study on blockchain implementation, particularly in the context of cryptocurrencies and their potential impact on various aspects of daily life, extensive development must be explored ^[21]. The principle of implementation for the confidentiality and security of data plays a significant role in money-based technology in lending and borrowing services in Indonesia. Ensuring the confidentiality and security of user data helps build trust, comply with regulations, and protect individuals' sensitive information. The gap identified in the study is that confidentiality and data security are crucial considerations

in lending and borrowing money today, where personal and financial information is susceptible to various forms of cyber threats and unauthorized access. The study on lending and borrowing money needs to address these aspects adequately ^[22].

Studies suggest that creating a sandbox regulation can certainly provide a framework to promote innovation and provide legal certainty for fintech firms, which can achieve a perfect result. An identified gap in a study related to unsuccessful Fintech organizers whose financial technology products do not meet regulatory standards and that prevented them from implementing their Fintech solutions ^[23]. The criteria or achievement factors for Information Technology projects in implementation development in the financial industry in the digitalization era, with a discussion of a case study of SIJAGO development in the PNMIM organization. The gap in this study is limited to projects in IT that measure the criteria of achievement factors in implementation development in the financial services with the SLR method and expert judgment ^[24].

Studies suggest that to address a particular challenge related to innovation and competition in the financial sector in Brazil, large traditional financial organizations are faced with two main options: creating fintech units internally or acquiring existing fintech companies in the Brazilian market. There was a gap in a study where the sample only included experts in their field from the established financial services in Brazil, neglecting all other stakeholders within the financial industry and broader society ^[25]. Identifying opportunities, challenges, and gaps for implementing and developing technology in regulation involves considering the potential benefits of regulatory solutions that recognize the obstacles that can hinder their successful adoption. A gap in not addressing topics related to Industry 4.0, blockchain, IoT (Internet of Things), and digitalized mechanisms ^[26].

This paper examines the importance of understanding e-commerce trends and the role of fintech. The potential of blockchain and cryptocurrency in revolutionizing e-commerce enables students to become proficient professionals. The gap identified in the study is related to establishing a trading commercial platform for educating students that focuses on the technical implementation of the platform while neglecting other important aspects ^[27]. The studies emphasize that technological and organizational indicators can help bank managers achieve a superior strategic technology approach. The gap identified in the study that focuses on fintech adoption and its implications for sustainability lacks attention to social and economic sustainability. It emphasizes environmental sustainability as one of the pillars ^[28].

Studies investigate and evaluate the level of fintech development in Latvia compared to Europe and explore three avenues that encourage platforms by working on a transparent system and promoting tax incentive investment. The gap in that study is limited to the possibilities and problems of implementation, the absence of a theoretical underpinning, and the not-covered risk of implementing Fintech ^[29]. The empirical study shows that adopting non-cash payment instruments, such as credit and debit cards, mobile payment applications, and electronic fund transfers, significantly impacts the instrument of cash payment and their role. The gap in that

study encompasses only security and data privacy issues in implementing mobile phones in e-money and addresses all other aspects ^[30].

The issue of the fintech development market, with its opportunities and obstacles, suggests public awareness and the development of a regulatory framework in the fintech market. A gap in the study does not incorporate risks that arise in the development and implementation of fintech in Ukraine and does not address issues in implementing fintech ^[31]. The focus on farmer adoption and accessibility is different in urban and rural areas due to the different levels of education, availability of infrastructure, and connectivity of the Internet in Indonesia. A study is limited to issues, access, and challenges faced by farmers when implementing fintech in the agriculture sector ^[32].

The paper discusses the use of policy instruments, policy enactment, and the effectiveness of policy changes for current development, the evolution path, and the implementation of fintech. It suggests to the government that it improve its fintech policies. A gap in the study is focused more on policy formation than on the application and technology part of fintech development, and there needs to be a part of the interaction of policy tools that needs evaluation for further studies ^[33]. The study works on three factors—technology, organization, and environment—that contribute to adopting innovation in financial services in small and medium enterprises, and the paper emphasizes policy implications for regulatory requirements. A gap in the study is limited to drivers of implementation of fintech, and further study is needed on the applicability and implementation of fintech in small and medium enterprises ^[34].

The study assesses the competitiveness of the adoption of Islamic fintech in various countries, and the study shows how the Islamic financial sector suffers losses that give reason to transform the operating model of a financial institution. The gap in the study is that a limited number of factors are considered that contribute to the fact that the specification of a model does not reflect the actual condition. Introduced five key factors that are: the capacity of established Islamic financial institutions; infrastructure facilities in ICT; environment operation; raising awareness; and ethics in finance ^[35]. The study focuses on fraudulent activities and cybercrime that increase the risk and interconnect with money laundering activities. The study examines financial regulators on cybersecurity issues for adopting and articulating emerging technology. Further, emphasize two areas where modern technology fits in banking or is adopted in the form of novel solutions or business models. A gap in the study is not conclusive to the performance review and effectiveness of financial regulators ^[36].

The study explores the indicator-related process and outcome of sustainable performance, which are the results of implementing fintech. The effective implementation of fintech leverages the bank and creates value in the innovative fintech era. Future studies have shaped fintech implementation, and their implications or modifications in testing and framework are the current need for future economic growth in developing countries ^[37].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study begins with a comprehensive overview of fintech. Researchers delve into reports, current news, and research papers to understand the pressing implementation problems in the fintech industry and to address the research question: What are the issues that hinder the effective implementation of fintech in India? The PRISMA technique, as depicted in Figure 1, is employed to conduct a systematic literature review. A Scopus and Web of Science search database is initiated for review up to 2024 to identify and screen relevant material. The search string is initiated with the keywords “Fintech AND Implementation AND Issues”, resulting in the retrieval of 84 articles from Scopus and 39 from Web of Science. After that, compare and analyze the search results, obtain Article 123, and add three relevant papers to the studies. This brings the total number of articles for the studies to 126. We apply specific inclusion or exclusion criteria, such as relevance to the Indian fintech industry and publication in reputable journals, for screening and remove 29 duplicate articles. Then, we review the title and abstract and select 41 articles that meet the eligibility criteria for full-text review. Further, 16 full-text articles not compatible with the studies should be removed, and three more papers should be included that give an Indian perspective on fintech implementation. Finally, we found the most significant 28 articles through the PRISMA technique. The study aims to determine issues that hinder the effective implementation of fintech in India.

Figure 1: PRISMA Flow ^[38].

4. ISSUE IN FINTECH IMPLEMENTATION

Fintech has tremendous advancements that have transformed the financial sector significantly. With effective implementation, fintech provides immense growth opportunities. Driving innovation in the market faces a substantial challenge for traditional financial services.

Businesses must develop strategies to integrate and implement financial technologies to impact fintech on the Indian economy. The Financial Industry must identify technological gaps early to achieve success in fintech implementation. Early detection allows for mitigating risks and costs associated with the technology adoption process, including cost, technology maturity, risks, and potential benefits. Vendor, adoption, technology, and reputation risks are essential for guiding decision-making for fintech implementation.

Another challenge is collaboration between traditional financial institutions and fintech firms. Adopting and implementing new technologies is time-intensive and complex to slow the pace of fintech adoption ^[39].

The question arises: How can companies effectively implement fintech solutions? The answer to knowing and evaluating the advantages and disadvantages at every stage—before, during, and after implementation is required for the profitability, sustainability, and growth of the fintech sector, where companies, shareholders, consumers, and investors make informed decisions, and the demand for dedicated resources within financial institutions slows the process of effective fintech implementation.

The fintech industry faces significant challenges during implementation due to regulatory concerns that overlapping rules and regulations create complexities that hinder the implementation of fintech in India. So, the need arises to standardize and harmonize the rules. Another major challenge the fintech market faces is securing adequate funding and support to execute and implement advanced technologies in financial services to grow the economy.

Table 1. ISSUES OF FINTECH IMPLEMENTATION AND THEIR IMPACT

Sources	Issues	Impact on Fintech Implementation
[27]	Handling cybersecurity regulation	By implying regulations, we need to build stakeholder trust and address data protection to safeguard privacy and security concerns.
[19]	reduced fraud risk, cybercrime, regulatory concern	Security and regulatory challenges hinder effective fintech implementation, limit knowledge, reduce efficiency, and undermine trust levels within MSMEs.
[37]	operation of firms, managerial level	The paper examines the challenges of firm operations and explores the managerial-level impact of fintech implementation on technology, organization, and environment.
[29]	Unawareness, strict licensing regulation	Strict licensing restrictions hinder the growth and development affecting fintech implementation. In Latvia, limited awareness about financial

		services leaves people unprepared to utilize them effectively.
[21]	Traditional Banking, Unpredictability of the market, error of humans, fraud, cybercrime, borrower not paying debt, security concerns, technical failure, malicious peer	Addressing the issue of collaboration between fintech and traditional banks hinders the legal and cybersecurity standards needed to implement fintech successfully.
[22]	illegal Fintech	Financial institutions not registered with the financial services authority are still obligated to regulate personal data that validates the protection of human rights.
[23]	ineffective regulatory sandbox	The uncertainty of legal concerns hinders the effective implementation of a regulatory sandbox.
[30]	security of data, privacy of customer	Data security and customer privacy concerns challenge the implementation of mobile e-money at PT Bank KEB Hana.
[40]	unqualified workforce, problems in interpretation, unavailable resources, unprofessional judgment, the limited infrastructure of technology, scared human resources, existing regulation policy not supportive	The paper addresses the challenges that hinder implementing fintech in the small and medium enterprise.
[25]	lack perception, fail to develop a regulatory framework, government restriction	The focus is more on fintech in niches where traditional financial businesses are nonexistent due to government-imposed entry barriers.
[41]	lack of access, illiteracy	The limited accessibility and high illiteracy rate in financial services hinder the development of underprivileged communities in Pakistan.

[31]	outdated and unfavorable regulation, collaboration problems, financial illiteracy, the transformation of digitalize cost, the process of a business complex, illiteracy of population, rejection of technology	All the problems present challenges and opportunities to create hindrances in innovation in implementing fintech.
[32]	differences in education level, unavailability of adequate infrastructure, differences in adoption, and accessibility in urban and rural, not ready to accept changes in the economy, fintech illiteracy, workers not willing and having adequate ability to utilize fintech, and limited law governing fintech.	The emphasis on issues, challenges, and access in the agriculture sector affects the effective implementation of fintech.
[35]	transformation of operating models in financial institutions, capacity to establish financial institutions, facilities of infrastructure, operating activities of environment, awareness & outreaching, and ethical finance	Managing the challenges reshapes the operating model, supports infrastructure development, and creates an environmental impact on the successful implementation of fintech.
[36]	cybersecurity issues for financial regulators, anti-fraud pertinent, pressurizing of meeting a set target, business model not to be tried, the uncertainty of regulation, excessive cost of compliance, the	A cybersecurity framework is essential for the successful implementation of fintech.

	brain of human overpower the big data, lack in skill of technology, losses in the trial of the visual audit.	
[10]	Cost, risk, security	Banks have collaborated with fintech companies to implement fintech solutions that cut costs, reduce risks, and address security challenges.

Source: author compilation

Table 1 identifies the issues of implementation of fintech through a review of papers and based on interpreting their impact on them.

5. IMPACT OF STAKEHOLDERS ON FINTECH IMPLEMENTATION

Inadequate implementation of fintech impacts stakeholders adversely, causing dissatisfaction, affecting the overall performance of the financial industry, and creating problems and difficulties for customers, investors, employees, regulators, and industry practitioners. Addressing these issues needs proper planning and execution for the successful implementation of fintech. Pre-considering challenges, risks, and issues arising in implementing fintech and the need for continuous striving to improve stakeholders' interests and needs for the financial industry's growth. Identifying Issues on Fintech Implementation affected by stakeholder perspective include employees, shareholders, consultants, managers, regulators, policymakers, and customers interacting with each other and having an interest in decision-making, profitability, and trends in fintech that impact the implementation of Fintech in India.

The author examines the impact of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors on fintech and non-fintech firms in the evolving and growing fintech sector from the perspectives of customers, employers, and investors. The author focuses on fintech firms that are not focusing on corporate sustainability, and studies emphasize ESG disclosure and its impact on stock performance ^[42]. The researcher emphasizes identifying the various stakeholders with concerns of interest and need and their impact of fintech and blockchain technology on the sports industry with their technological advancement ^[43].

6. CONCLUSION

According to reports, around 87% of Indians are adopting fintech, which shows that the fintech industry has tremendous growth potential in the financial sector. Studies show that increasing growth and opportunities have shown significant challenges and issues for implementing fintech in India, which is why fintech companies suffer losses. Here, the researcher explored the reasons for inadequate implementation through an in-depth literature review and addressed this complex issue of implementing fintech. Financial stakeholders benefit from implementing fintech in India, including regulators, employees, shareholders, policymakers, industrialists, and customers. Studies emphasize theoretical as well as practical

implications. For further studies, the researcher strongly suggests the need for a framework to overcome the issue of fintech implementation in India. This clear direction for future research keeps the readers focused. This study is limited to addressing the issue of the implementation of fintech in India.

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Availability of data and material

Not Applicable

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REFERENCES

1. Ngo, A. E. (2023). Formulation of Strategic Plan for a Financial Technology Startup Company. *International Journal of Academe and Industry Research*, 4(1), 46–79. <https://doi.org/10.53378/352974>
2. K. Srinivasan, & Dr. S. Rajarajeswari. (2021). Financial Technology in Indian Finance Market. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 11(2), 206–211. <https://doi.org/10.31033/ijemr.11.2.29>
3. Pandey, D. K., Hassan, M. K., Kumari, V., Zaied, Y. Ben, & Rai, V. K. (2024). Mapping the landscape of FinTech in banking and finance: A bibliometric review. In *Research in International Business and Finance* (Vol. 67). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2023.102116>

4. Lagna, A., & Ravishankar, M. N. (2022). Making the world a better place with fintech research. *Information Systems Journal*, 32(1), 61–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12333>
5. Shin, Y. J., & Choi, Y. (2019). Feasibility of the fintech industry as an innovation platform for sustainable economic growth in Korea. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11195351>
6. *INDIAN FINTECH Q1/2023 InFocus B2B Lending*.
7. in India, K. (2016). *Fintech in India - A global growth story*.
8. García-Arango, D. A., Echeverri Gutiérrez, C. A., Echeverri Gutiérrez, M. S., & González, M. Y. F. (2024). Implementation of a process innovation for the automation, optimization and development of technological capabilities for the FinTech sector in the firm TIENDACOL S.A.S. | Implementación de una innovación de proceso para la automatización, optimización y . *RISTI - Revista Iberica de Sistemas e Tecnologias de Informacao*, 2024(E68), 620–637.
9. Malladi, C. M., Soni, R. K., & Srinivasan, S. (2021). Digital financial inclusion: next frontiers—challenges and opportunities. *CSI Transactions on ICT*, 9(2), 127–134. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40012-021-00328-5>
10. Kloba, L. (2024). IMPLEMENTATION OF FINTECH IS THE BANK'S COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE. *Financial and Credit Activity: Problems of Theory and Practice*, 3(56), 38–48. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptop.3.56.2024.4368>
11. Anusha Rajan, V. R., & Mohapatra, L. M. (2024). Implementation of FinTech Solution in Banking: Navigating through Critical Assessment and Research Agenda. *Proceedings - International Conference on Computing, Power, and Communication Technologies, IC2PCT 2024*, 281–286. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IC2PCT60090.2024.10486443>
12. Schueffel, P. (2016). Taming the Beast: A Scientific Definition of Fintech. *Journal of Innovation Management Schueffel JIM*, 4, 32–54.
13. Sangwan, V., Harshita, Prakash, P., & Singh, S. (2020). Financial technology: a review of extant literature. In *Studies in Economics and Finance* (Vol. 37, Issue 1, pp. 71–88). Emerald Group Holdings Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SEF-07-2019-0270>
14. Martincevic, I., Crnjevic, S., & Klopotan, I. (2022). Novelties and Benefits of Fintech in the Financial Industry. *International Journal of E-Services and Mobile Applications*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJESMA.2022010107>

15. Sahabuddin, M., Sakib, M. N., Rahman, M. M., Jibir, A., Fahlevi, M., Aljuaid, M., & Grabowska, S. (2023). The Evolution of FinTech in Scientific Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097176>
16. Hornuf, L., Klus, M. F., Lohwasser, T. S., & Schwienbacher, A. (2021). How do banks interact with fintech startups? *Small Business Economics*, 57(3), 1505–1526. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-020-00359-3>
17. Thakor, A. V. (2020). Fintech and banking: What do we know? *Journal of Financial Intermediation*, 41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfi.2019.100833>
18. Lagna, A., & Ravishankar, M. N. (2022). Making the world a better place with fintech research. *Information Systems Journal*, 32(1), 61–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/isj.12333>
19. Tjahjanto, Lestari, I. R., Meidiyustiani, R., & Imelda. (2020). Implementation of technology, efficiency, knowledge, risk on trust level of fintech used in MSMEs in Tangerang City. *Proceedings of the International Conference on IT, Communication and Technology for Better Life, ICT4BL 2019*, 122–125. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0008930401220125>
20. Putri, M. F., Juita, R., Nidayanto, A. N., & Inan, D. I. (2022). Gamification on Mobile Payment Application: Uses and Gratification Perspective. *Asia Pacific Journal of Information Systems*, 32(4), 750–769. <https://doi.org/10.14329/APJIS.2022.32.4.750>
21. Stojakovic-Celustka, S. (2022). FinTech and Its Implementation. In *Communications in Computer and Information Science: Vol. 1694 CCIS*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22228-3_12
22. Wahyuni, S. (2019). Implementation of Confidentiality and Data Security in the Execution of the Lending and Borrowing Money Service Based on Information Technology in Indonesia. In *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*. www.ijicc.net (Vol. 10, Issue 5). www.ijicc.net
23. Yuspin, W., Resty, Y., Putri, A., & Ikbal, M. Legal Certainty on Financial Technology Organisers: Perspective of Regulatory Sandbox Implementation. In *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*. www.ijicc.net (Vol. 12, Issue 2). www.ijicc.net
24. Trisnawaty, N. W., Raharjo, T., Hardian, B., & Prasetyo, A. (2021, April 21). Success criteria and factor for IT project application implementation in digital transformation era: A case study financial sector industry. *2021 IEEE International IOT, Electronics and Mechatronics Conference, IEMTRONICS 2021 - Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEMTRONICS52119.2021.9422578>

25. Joia, L. A., & Proença, R. (2022). The social representation of fintech from the perspective of traditional financial sector professionals: evidence from Brazil. *Financial Innovation*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40854-022-00409-7>
26. Nasir, A., Shaukat, K., Khan, K. I., Hameed, I. A., Alam, T. M., & Luo, S. (2021). Trends and directions of financial technology (Fintech) in society and environment: A bibliometric study. *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, 11(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app112110353>
27. Yau, P. C., Luen, W. H., Leung, J., & Wong, D. (2020). Practicing Mobile-Commerce as a Pro-Implementation of an Education-oriented Commercial Trading System. *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 135–139. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3409929.3416794>
28. Taneja, S., Siraj, A., Ali, L., Kumar, A., Luthra, S., & Zhu, Y. (2023). Is FinTech Implementation a Strategic Step for Sustainability in Today; Changing Landscape; An Empirical Investigation. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2023.3262742>
29. Saksonova, S., & Kuzmina-Merlino, I. (2017). Fintech as Financial Innovation-The Possibilities and Problems of Implementation. In *European Research Studies Journal: Vol. XX*.
30. Haryadi, D., Harisno, Kusumawardhana, V. H., & Warnars, H. L. H. S. (2019). The Implementation of E-money in Mobile Phone: A Case Study at PT Bank KEB Hana. *1st 2018 Indonesian Association for Pattern Recognition International Conference, INAPR 2018 - Proceedings*, 202–206. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INAPR.2018.8627055>
31. Vartsaba, V., & Zaslavska, O. (2020). FINTECH INDUSTRY IN UKRAINE: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 6(4), 46–55. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2020-6-4-46-55>
32. Rufaidah, F., Karyani, T., Wulandari, E., & Setiawan, I. (2023). A Review of the Implementation of Financial Technology (Fintech) in the Indonesian Agricultural Sector: Issues, Access, and Challenges. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(3), 108. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs11030108>
33. Yin, Y., Ma, H., Wu, Z., & Yue, A. (2023). How Does China Build Its Fintech Strategy? A Perspective of Policy Evolution. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(13). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151310100>

34. Moreira-Santos, D., Au-Yong-Oliveira, M., & Palma-Moreira, A. (2022). Fintech Services and the Drivers of Their Implementation in Small and Medium Enterprises. *Information (Switzerland)*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/info13090409>
35. Glavina, S., Aidrus, I., & Trusova, A. (2021). Assessment of the Competitiveness of Islamic Fintech Implementation: A Composite Indicator for Cross-Country Analysis. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm14120602>
36. Ng, A. W., & Kwok, B. K. B. (2017). Emergence of Fintech and cybersecurity in a global financial centre: Strategic approach by a regulator. In *Journal of Financial Regulation and Compliance* (Vol. 25, Issue 4, pp. 422–434). Emerald Group Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRC-01-2017-0013>
37. Taneja, S., Siraj, A., Ali, L., Kumar, A., Luthra, S., & Zhu, Y. (2024). Is FinTech Implementation a Strategic Step for Sustainability in Today's Changing Landscape? An Empirical Investigation. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 71, 7553–7565. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2023.3262742>
38. Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Systematic Reviews*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01626-4>
39. *Implementing FinTech: A Guide to Overcoming Barriers*. (2020).
40. Hamdani, N. A., Herlianti, A. O., & Amin, A. S. (2019). Society 5.0: Feasibilities and challenges of the implementation of fintech in small and medium industries. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1402(7). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1402/7/077053>
41. Noreen, M., Mia, M. S., Ghazali, Z., & Ahmed, F. (2022). Role of Government Policies to Fintech Adoption and Financial Inclusion: A Study in Pakistan. *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 10(1), 37–46. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujaf.2022.100105>
42. Atayah, O. F., Najaf, K., Ali, M. H., & Marashdeh, H. (2023). Sustainability, market performance and FinTech firms. *Meditari Accountancy Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-08-2021-1405>
43. Glebova, E., & Mihaľová, P. (2023). New currencies and new values in professional sports: blockchain, NFT, and fintech through the stakeholder approach. *Journal of*

Physical Education and Sport, 23(5), 1244–1252.
<https://doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2023.05153>